

PUBLIC SERVICE DELIVERY: FOREIGN EXPERIENCE

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Abstract:

This article examines foreign experience in the provision of public services. The authors analyze modern approaches, technologies, and institutional mechanisms used in the organization and provision of public services in different countries. In particular, attention will be paid to best practices aimed at increasing the efficiency, transparency, and accessibility of services for citizens. The article also examines the possibilities of adapting foreign models to the conditions of Uzbekistan and provides practical recommendations. This study is important for specialists in the field of public administration and public services, as well as those interested in this topic.

Keywords: government services, foreign experience, public administration, efficiency, transparency, technologies, institutional mechanisms, Uzbekistan, public services, adaptation of models.

In relations with the state, citizens' rights and guarantees of their observance, as well as their participation in governance, the transparency of administrative organizations, their responsiveness and accessibility to people, the ease of obtaining information for citizens, and other issues are becoming increasingly relevant. In general, the partial revision of the basic principles of public service that has been taking place in the West in recent decades can be explained by the following main directions:

firstly, direct involvement in the preparation, adoption, and (or) implementation of decisions in the field of executive and directive activities of the state by type of work, in connection with which, in a number of cases, these actions entail significant economic and other social consequences for society as a whole or for some part of it;

secondly, the civil servant's right and opportunity to represent a state body (and thus, as if in the guise of the state) within the framework of their powers, representing state interests;

thirdly, the combination of strictly regulated activity in official procedural relations, which has significantly broader decision-making possibilities based on both the situation and the subjective interpretation of regulatory legal norms;

fourthly, (and this is not the least in importance) belonging to a specific group with professional status, united by the fact that representatives of different professions work in government bodies. This implies that persons belonging to this group have certain state-power authorities and, thereby, have significantly greater opportunities to influence the development of affairs in society and, consequently, bear greater responsibility than the majority of persons with the same type of citizenship.

In our opinion, the main direction of improving the culture of public service today is its "spiritualization," that is, strengthening attention to the moral and spiritual aspects of civil

servants' behavior. For example, in many countries, a code of conduct for employees, containing both legal and moral norms, either exists or is being implemented. Any administrative reform without a moral component is considered unlikely to succeed.

In Bulgarian administrative law, the concept of "state service" is understood in the narrow sense of the word - as the performance of administrative and managerial functions in state institutions, that is, in institutions funded by the state budget. Modern concepts of public service are based on the relevant provisions of the Constitution and the interpretations of the Constitutional Court of Bulgaria. The term "state service" is mentioned several times in the Bulgarian Constitution[1]. For example, Clause 2 of Article 65 stipulates that "candidates for people's representation who are in state service shall terminate this service after registration." Clause 1 of Article 68 states: "People's representatives cannot hold other state offices," and Clause 2 clarifies: "A people's representative appointed as a minister suspends his representative powers during his ministerial term."

In Germany, as in a number of other countries, public service is literally translated as "public" service[2]. This concept encompasses all employees in government institutions. This includes not only employees of governing bodies, but also teachers, preschool staff, professors and lecturers of state universities, judges, ministers, members of the Federal Bank's board of directors, as well as police officers, military personnel, railway employees, postal workers, and others.

In France, all employees of the state as a public legal entity are civil servants working in legislative, executive, and judicial bodies both in the capital and outside it. In addition to the state service, a public service for local communities was also established, which is regulated separately by the Law of 1984[3].

The foundations of modern civil service in Great Britain were laid as early as 1850-1870. At that time, open competitive examinations for entering the civil service were introduced, and the Civil Service Commission, independent of other administrative bodies, was established as the governing body of the employee selection system.

Modern civil service in the United States began in 1883 with the Civil Service Act[5]. This document abolished the previous "spoils" system, according to which the president who won the elections could completely replace all officials.

In Japan, the civil service covers the administrative, diplomatic, and judicial spheres of state activity. Here, it is customary to include in the category of civil servants not only officials in the literal sense of the word, but also employees of state-owned enterprises, employees of state railways, television, public schools, military personnel of the "self-defense forces," and police officers.

The total number of people employed in the civil service is more than three million people, most of whom are workers and employees who do not have a clear opportunity to make managerial decisions[6]. The number of civil servants does not exceed ten thousand people[7].

The civil service in Singapore was officially established in 1955, but in fact its history began in 1819 with the founding of Singapore by the British. The acquisition of the right to local self-government within the framework of the British colonial empire, the achievement of independence in 1965, did not have a serious impact on the organization of public service.

In many countries, laws aimed at regulating public service relations have been adopted. For example, Article 2 of the Law of the Russian Federation "On the Fundamentals of Public

Service in the Russian Federation" of July 5, 1995, defines public service as professional activity carried out to ensure the powers of state bodies. It should be noted here that official duties belong not to the civil service, but to civil servants. Here one can see a specific aspect of the concept of public service.

According to Article 2 of the Law of the Republic of Belarus "On Public Service in the Republic of Belarus" of June 14, 2003, public service is understood as professional activity aimed at the direct exercise of state power powers and (or) ensuring the performance of the functions of state bodies while holding a state position.

According to Article 1 of the Law of the Republic of Kazakhstan "On Public Service" of July 23, 1999, public service is the activity of civil servants in state bodies for the performance of official powers aimed at implementing the tasks and functions of state power[8].

According to the Law of the Kyrgyz Republic "On Public Service" of August 11, 2004, public service is the activity of civil servants carried out in state bodies on a professional basis and aimed at fulfilling the tasks, functions, and powers of power defined by the Constitution and other normative acts.

Based on the content of legislative acts, the legislation of some states defines public service as a professional activity aimed at carrying out the tasks and functions of the state (state bodies) by a person holding a certain position in a state body. Legal literature also provides for several specific features aimed at revealing the essence of public service.

Analysis of best practices in the provision of public services shows that Estonia deserves special recognition in this regard. In particular, according to the results of the study, Estonia has implemented the electronic citizenship platform "e-Residence," through which applications and complaints on citizenship issues are accepted. In particular, a person can access the website <https://e-residence.pro/er/create> via the Internet and formulate citizenship-related appeals[9]. An electronic registration system has also been organized for taking the exam to determine the level of knowledge of the Constitution and the state language[10].

In Far Western countries, the distribution of powers in civil proceedings is somewhat different. For example, in Bulgaria, citizenship matters fall under the jurisdiction of the President and the Ministry of Justice, while in Greece, these powers belong to the mayor, self-governing bodies, and the Ministry of Internal Affairs. In Austria, the federal government and the Ministry of Internal Affairs, in Canada, the State Secretariat, which includes the Bureau of Citizenship, in Australia, the Department of Immigration and Interethnic Relations, and in the USA, the courts are recognized as competent bodies in this area. In China, the powers under consideration were transferred to the Ministries of Public Security and State Security[11]. In Turkey, powers on matters of citizenship are distributed between the Cabinet of Ministers, the Ministries of Internal Affairs, Foreign Affairs, and Justice[12].

The experience of Kazakhstan on the issue under analysis (Article 496) [13] shows that the unlawful use of a passport of citizenship of the Republic of Kazakhstan and an identity document by persons who have lost citizenship of Kazakhstan and failure of persons who have acquired citizenship of another state to notify the authorized state bodies of this fact within the established time limits entails administrative liability.

Russian legislation (Article 19.8.3 of the RF Code of Administrative Responsibility) [14] establishes administrative liability for failure to report or providing false information about obtaining foreign citizenship or a residence permit.

According to the Administrative Code of Armenia (Articles 195 (1), 195 (2)), a) if a citizen resides abroad for more than 6 months and does not notify the Ministry of Foreign Affairs (consular institutions) of Armenia about this, he is subject to a fine of 50 percent or one minimum wage; b) if he does not notify the government of Armenia about the acceptance of foreign citizenship, he is subject to a fine of 50 minimum wages[15].

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